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Patching up Risks? – A View on Human Factors and Toxic Fumes

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Extended Abstract

Historically aviation is known for improving and enhancing the design of aircraft, from the 1980's Ground Proximity Warning System (GPWS) until today's advanced automation with reduced separation allowing for more traffic. Sometimes however, the system behaves in ways that the designers did not think of – an example of this is the B737 MAX, or an oil leak affecting the air quality and the people working onboard an aircraft. Very often the design is finished by the most adaptive element in a system – the people, and we may not even notice that the design was flawed in the first place.

But what assumptions lie around risk, when we talk about toxic fumes in the aircraft? Diane Vaughan (1986, p. 62) tells us that "Risk is in the eye of the beholder" and it seems that the risk associated with toxic fumes depends on the eyes looking at it. From a regulatory point, there seems to be different views on the risk associated with toxic fumes. While ICAO (2015, p. 1) states: "... particular concerns have been raised regarding the negative impact on flight safety when crew members are exposed to oil or hydraulic fluid fumes or smoke and experience acute symptoms in flight", EASA 2017 seems to come from a different perspective: "Contaminated air is not a flight safety issue. The air quality on a passenger jet aircraft is similar or better than what is observed in normal indoor environments".

Yet, an increase in reports of smell, smoke and fumes have increased over the last five years (AAIB 2020) and from investigating numerous fume events, common features have been identified. These common features suggest a systemic design flaw not presently accounted for, and for the people involved this emergent system property changes the risk profile.

Humans adapt to make things work. Most of the time things go well, because humans in the system are fantastic, through their ability to adapt and adjust their performance to patch up systems imperfections and messy details that seems to go beyond the designs in the system, in ultimately sustaining the daily operation. But this adaptability is finite (Woods 2015) and susceptible to outer factors influencing. Humans make an enormous contribution to safety, but certain designs in work structures, equipment and tools needs to be in place for the sharp end people to do their job in a safety critical environment.

Checklist serves to aid the pilots as simplified means in abnormal situations, like a toxic fume event. Toxic fumes are often not associated with smoke but smell, and often appear suddenly with rapid effect on the crew. The design of

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some checklist in regards to smoke/fumes therefore seems to be incomplete as these are “geared towards identification and isolation of any possible source of smoke in the airplane. Therefore it is not suited to determine and eliminate the various causes of smell” (BFU 2015).

From AAI Bulletin (AAIB 2000) an example of how the pilots patch up the deficiencies of the system seems to rely on their previous experience. The report states that both pilots had been exposed to toxic fumes before, which they had discussed the evening before. “The flight crew’s previous experience suggested that if the smell was going to re-occur, it was most likely to occur when thrust was reduced for descent, so during the cruise they discussed their actions if the smell returned and reviewed the SMOKE/FUMES/AVNCS Checklist” (AAIB 2020, p. 2). One may ask whether we can rely on sufficient experience being present on the flight deck to prevent harm? And whether this responsibility should be placed in the hands of the pilots?

What perhaps seems to go unrecognized is how people are the most adaptable element in a complex work system, and what this means to the wider system – like systems safety. “People are the most adaptable element in any complex work system. This adaptability is essential in making things work, both in ordinary but especially in extraordinary circumstances” (Wears 2013, p. 338). Safety is not something we have, safety is something we do, and dependent upon the adaptive capacity present. One may wonder, are we willing to trade this adaptive capacity and ignore the signals of risk from the sharp end people, research and investigations, at the expense of safety and employee’s health and well being?

This text suggests that design improvement is required, in order not to jeopardize the health and well-being of the employees. “Users should not have to adapt to support systems, rather systems should adapt to support users” (Wears 2013, p. 1).

Keywords

risk, human factors, fume event, toxic fumes, flight safety, health, adaptability

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Gitte Furdal Damm is a former captain on the ATR 72-600 and has been working at various Danish Airlines such as Cimber Air and Jettime. Since 2015 she has been a CRM Trainer and is the owner of About Human Factors, which provides CRM courses in aviation. She is currently also attending the MSc program in Human Factors and System Safety at Lund University.